

EFFECT OF GARA VISHA AND DUSHI VISHA ON HUMANS IN THE CURRENT ERA**Dr. Imran*¹, Dr. Tejendra Singh²**¹Assistant Professor, Department of Agad Tantra Evam Vidhi Vaidyaka, Krishna Ayurvedic Medical College & Hospital, Bijnor, U.P.²Assistant Professor, Department of Swasthavritta & Yoga, Krishna Ayurvedic Medical College & Hospital, Bijnor, U.P.**How to cite this Article:** Dr. Imran*¹, Dr. Tejendra Singh² (2026). Effect Of Gara Visha And Dushi Visha On Humans In The Current Era. World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research, 12(1), 496–500.
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ABSTRACT

Ayurveda gives more importance to the promotion of health and prevention of disease rather than the treatment of disease. Poison is in everything; only the dose decides its effects. One of the hidden poisons is the concocted poison known as Gara Visha. Ayurveda explains this Visha as the combination of poisonous or non-poisonous substances that produces chronic toxicity by interfering with the process of digestion. People unknowingly consume various combinations of substances that are harmful to health. The insect powder and human waste products are some of the agents of Gara Visha. Many food items consumed daily contain some natural toxins. By knowing these food items can be reduced the chances of toxicity. Ayurveda defines Gara Visha in a marvellous way and describes the treatment as well, like Vamana Karma, Agadpana. Ayurveda plays an important role in the management of Gara Visha. Dushi Visha is one of the unique concepts explained in Ayurveda. It is a type of toxin which remains inside the body for long & then produces various ill effects on the body. In the present era, people are exposed to various toxins in their day-to-day lives, which is causing various health problems. There are many such illnesses where treatment does not work, as it is not eliminate the root cause. The ancient concept of Dushi Visha seems to be more relevant in this context. So this topic is selected to study the concept comprehensively with the object of highlighting it with a modern approach.

KEYWORDS: Ayurveda, Gara Visha, Dushi Visha, Cumulative poison, Concocted poison, Polluting poison.**INTRODUCTION**

Majority of poison accumulation occurring in our body today is even without our knowledge as a result of change in lifestyle. In Ayurveda, while described Visha, Visha classified in various category such as Sthavar, Jangam, Gara Visha, Dushi Visha etc. which has not been removed completely from the body or whose potency has been reduced either by Agni or Vayu or Aatapa or due to the effect of the antidotes. Gara Visha is a combination of toxic or non-toxic substances and Chakrapani defines Dushi Visha as “Kalantara Prakopi Visham Dushi Visham” means it manifests the symptoms afterwards.

The concept of Dushi Visha and Gara Visha explained in our classics is more relevant to the present day. Gara Visha and Dushi Visha are like a cumulative poison is a slow acting one, which is not fully eliminated from the system and because of this, it affects all Dhatus gradually,

when it enters to Rakta Dhatu, it produces toxicity in Raktavaha Srotas which leads to Arunshika, Kitibh and Kotha.

In present scenario people are more prone to various kind of poison, including slow poison in food as well as in environment as poison which is old attenuated by anti-poisonous medicines or dried by forest fire, breeze and the sunlight or naturally deficient is properties of the poison is defined as Dushi Visha. It is not fatal due to mild potency and being covered with Kapha. It stays in body for many years. Heavy metals like mercury, arsenic, lead, titanium, zinc etc. are continuously gaining their entry into our body, owing to the increased use to pesticides, fertilizers and other industrial products, automobile exhaust.

The mode of entry of metals may be through diet, medication, environment, occupation or hobbies. Food

and drug occurring in large scale is nothing but the Gara Visha explained by our Acharyas. Sushruta advice Shodhan i.e. Vamana and Virechana to remove accumulated toxins from the body, also mentions the usage of Dushi Vishari Agada on daily basis.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This article based on different Ayurvedic texts, contemporary literature journals, e-journals, internet, and other available sources.

Literature Review

Gara Visha – According to Acharya Charaka, “A Poison formed by combination of different poison or concocted poison finds its reference under Gara Visha other than the basic classification of Visha as Sthavara and Jangama Visha”. Because of the delayed digestion property of this Visha these are not immediately fatal.

Acharya Sushruta and Acharya Vagbhata opines that the poison which is formed from the waste materials from the animals or combination of medicines or Bhasma which are having opposite properties or the poisons having the less potency can be considered as Gara Visha. According to Acharya Kashyapa the poison formed by the combinations of the Churna form of the several insects is considered as Gara Visha. In ancient times Visha kanya used to kill the enemies or for poisoning can be categorized under this heading only. A women desiring success in love would mix their sweat or raja in food etc & give to their husbands.

Signs of Gara Visha: It takes approximately 15 days to 1 month for the signs to appear after the ingestion of the Garavisha. Some of the symptoms like pale and weak body, loss of appetite, tachycardia, Edema in the extremities, Garahani, Rajayakshma, Gulma, Dhatukshaya, Jwara etc. will start to appear are suggestive of Gara Visha poisoning.

Gara Visha Chikitsa

- According to Acharya Charak
 - Hridya Shodhan - Vamana Karma with Tamra Churana mixed with honey.
 - Sawarn Prashan - after Vamana Karma patient should be given Sawarn Bhasama with Madhu.
 - Agadapaana - Nagadantiyadi Ghrita.
- According to Acharya Vagabhatta
 - Vamana Karma
 - Sharkarasuvarnaadi Leha
 - Moorvaadiguduchiaadi Churna
 - Paravataadi Hima.

Dushi Visha

Acharya Chakrapani defines Dushi Visha as ‘Kalantara Prakopi Visham Dushi Visham’ means it manifests the symptom afterwords.^[1]

The term ‘Dushi Visha’ is compound of two different

words ‘Dushi’ and ‘Visha’.

Dushi means denatured, attenuated, altered, latent, vitiated or something which influences the system in the long run. Visha means poison.

The word Dushi Visha is derived from the word ‘Dushti’. Meaning polluting or defiling. It means which pollutes many time.^[2,3]

The poison which vitiates Dhatus because of factors such as Desh, Kaal, Aahara and Nidra during day time is called Dushi Visha.^[4]

In the present scenario people are more prone to various kind of poison, including slow poison in food as well as in environment. Poison which is old attenuated by anti poisonous medicines or dried by forest fire, breeze and the sunlight or naturally deficient in properties of the poison is defined as Dushi Visha. It is not fatal due to mild potency and being covered with Kapha, it stays in body for many years.^[5]

As Dushi Visha is a low potent slowly progressing poison it affects all dhatus gradually. When it enters to Rakta Dhatu it produce toxicity in Raktavah Srotas which leads to different types of Kustha (Twak Vikara), Kitibh, Kandu, Arunshika, Kotha.^[6]

Dadru (Dermatophytosis) is Pittakapha Pradhan Kustha having clinical features Kandu (Itching), Raga (Erythema), Pidika (Eruptions) and Utsanna Mandala (Elevated circular skin lesion).

Signs of Dushivisha^[7] - Then it causes a sense of intoxication after meals, indigestion, aversion for food, circular patches and urticarial rashes on the skin, stupor, loss of essential constituents of the body, swelling of the feet, hands and face, ascites, vomiting and then diarrhoea, discoloration, fainting, intermittent pyrexia and excessively increased thirst. Some of poisons produce insanity, some of them cause obstipation, some cause loss of semen, while others lead to blurred speech, leprosy and various other similar disease.

Factors Aggravating Dushi Visha^[8] Polluted Land (Dushita Desha), Deranged Seasons (Kala), Toxic Food (Anna) & Daytime Sleep (Diwaswapna) are factors that aggravate Dushi Visha.

According to Acharya Vagbhata -exposure to Pragvata (eastern wind), indigestion, cold weather, cloudy days, day sleep Intake of unwholesome food also aggravate Dushi Visha. Polluted Land.

(Dushita Desha): Polluted land can be considered as wet, watery or humid land (Anupa Desha) where excess wind, cold weather & increased rain falls is present. Such land (Anupa Desha) influences on Kapha dosha & leads to aggravation of poison in the body as latent poison.

Chikitsa of Dushi visha

- Ajeya Ghrita
- Dushi Vishaari Agada.

This treatment is useful in Dushi Visha and other poisonous condition.

Symptomatic treatments for complications

Acharya Sushruta - The patients should be given Swedana then the following Agada may be administered for a few days viz. Pippali, Jatamaansi, Lodhra, Mushta, Laghu, Ela and Suvarna Gairik with honey.

This treatment should be given between episodes. During an episode symptomatic treatment is indicated.^[9] Similarly, Astanga Sangrahaakar also explained that the patient of Dushi Visha should be administered sudation therapy and then the emesis and purgation therapies followed by licking of Dushivishari Agada (antidote) mix with honey as same as Sushruta explained in Kalpasthana. only 4 more content is added by Astang Sangrahaakara i.e., Nata, Kutnata, Kustha, Yasti, Chandana with honey.^[10]

Acharya Charaka - If the patient is affected with Dushivisha or if the poison is located in the blood, then he should be given Sirovedhana (Venesection) therapy and panchakarma (Five types of elimination therapy).^[11]

The physician should prepare therapies and administer them, along keeping in view all the aspects of the situation. In the beginning, the Dosha of the locality (where the poison located) should be carefully alleviated so that the effects of poison which is located there are not augmented.

Updarava of Dushi Visha^[12] – Jwara, Ushma, Hikka, Aadhmaan, Hruhdayroga, Shukra-kshaya, Padshotha, Atisaara, Glani, Vandhyatwa. They may be treated appropriately.

A view through Modern Review – While the effect of industrialization and commercialization are widely and rapidly spreading in the society, the chances of contacts with toxins are also increasing. With the change in life style of modern civilized man, the risk of getting exposure to the poisons like Gara Visha and Dshi Visha are also increasing day by day. There are so many sectors that can be compared to Gara Visha in today's society, the prevalence of which is very high.

The sectors are

- Adulteration / preservatives
- Cosmetics
- Psychoactive drugs
- Occupational poisoning

Toxicity by improper preparation of different Bhasmas (nanotoxicology) In today's society many food items are adulterated by many factors. Even milk, what we know as the purest is also adulterated. Now-a-days, food

preservatives have a very extensive use. Many of these appear to be innocuous but there is danger in continuous use of food preserved by these agents. Carbonated cold drinks are actually a combination of phosphoric acid, sugar, caffeine, colouring agent, heavy metals and flavouring agents. Now-a-days vegetables and fruits also contain chemicals beyond permissible limits. In agricultural practice also the use of chemical fertilizers, pesticides^[13] etc. pollute their growing land, poison the nearby water source and leave their residues in the food stuff. By taking these food products many harmful chemicals enter into the body which can cause acute, chronic or cumulative toxicity, trans dermally causing local as well as systemic problems.

Under the concept of Gara Visha we can also include psychoactive drugs the use of which is in the peak level in today's society. For e.g., various sedatives, allopathic medicines, alcohol, drugs^[14] etc. these are having direct toxic effect on certain tissues like brain and liver and in psychological cause mood alteration, anxiety, irritability, depression, cerebral atrophy etc.

Another sector in modern field i.e., occupational poisoning can also be comparable to Gara Visha It is occurring due to the accidental exposure to poison through skin, eyes, nose, mouth etc. It may simulate many other disorders. It usually lacks a unique pathology and marked by long lat period between exposure and manifestation. It chiefly embraces the employment in industries, factories, mines, forestry and agriculture which are very common in the current scenario.

As per the texts various Bhasmas can be used as Gara Visha. Effect of these Bhasmas can be understood in nanotoxicology level.^[15] This technique of using nanomaterials for therapeutic purposes is used in Ayurveda to prepare herbo mineral preparations. Of these will not be prepared in a proper way which is very commonly happening now-a-days, it will produce toxic symptoms. After getting inside the body either Gara Visha or Dushi Visha cannot be fully metabolized and undergoes improper digestion and improper assimilation. As a result, it cannot be properly expelled out from the body and get accumulated as toxins. As inside the body liver performs the detoxification function ultimately these toxins affect the liver. Being the major drug metabolizing and detoxifying organ the liver is subjected to potential damage from these toxins and thus ultimately diseases related to liver is being produced. Now-a-days also the diseases like hepatic failure, hepatic encephalopathy, drug and toxic induced liver diseases and alcoholic liver diseases are very common not only whose signs and symptoms resemble to Gara Visha but in aetiology also this concept is very much responsible for hepatopathy.^[16] As it is known that Dushi Visha as such after getting inside the body immediately cannot manifest. Any poison (may be Sthavara, Jangama or Kritrima Visha) after exposure remain inside the body and in favourable conditions only get vitiated and manifest the symptoms.

These favourable conditions include Dushita Desha, Kaala, Anna, Jatharaagni, Divaswapna, Ahitashana etc. In recent days already pollution has taken as an important risk factor for mankind, it includes pollution of land, air and water, the factors responsible for aggravation of Dushi Visha. The pollution of all these factors and use of fertilizers,^[17] chemicals, pesticides etc. in agriculture ultimately leads to the deposition of toxins in foods which in turn get into the body. Alteration of living style, food habits, exposure to different toxins etc. interfere in the digestive power of a person and due to all these factors. the Jatharaagni become weak which even cannot be able to digest light food particles thus giving rise to Amadosha, the root cause of various illnesses. In today's youth, it is the general trend to remain awake up to late night and to sleep in the day time and also taking fast foods, cold drinks, different food combinations which are nothing but Viruddha Ahara. All these altered faulty modern life style only leads to aggravation of toxins present inside the body giving rise to different simple to grave disuses. About Dushi Visha it can be told that the toxins, which are exposed in present world, are having their effects on different systems of the body. As these are low potency poisons, cannot harm to the body as such and once absorbed after improper metabolism, remain as such or in the form metabolites within the body for variable periods and gradually distributed to various organs, thus of causing organic systemic disorders of various ranges. All most all the poisons can act as Dushi Visha.

The following sectors in present modern world may attribute to Dushi Visha in greater extent.

- Insect bite
- Inanimate poison
- Viruddha Ahara and Ahit Ahara
- Fast foods and cold beverages like colas
- Alcohol, tobacco etc.
- Drugs like quinine, NSAIDS, steroids etc.
- Pesticides, heavy metals, minerals, pollutants etc.^[18]

DISCUSSION

In present scenario people are more prone to various kind of poison, including slow poison in food as well as in environment poison which is old attenuated by anti-poisonous medicines or dried by forest fire, breeze and the sunlight or naturally deficient is properties of the poison is defined as Dushi Visha. It is not fatal due to mild potency and being covered with Kapha. It stay in body for many years. Heavy metals like mercury, arsenic, lead, titanium, zinc etc. are continuously gaining their entry into our body, owing to the increased use to pesticides, fertilizers and other industrial products, automobile exhaust.

CONCLUSION

The concept of Gara Visha and Dushi Visha are gaining importance in present era. Both these may be the causes for the decreasing health status of the society. These are generally everyday being absorbed into our body through

various means. Hence applying these two basic principles of Ayurveda from the treatment aspect as well as from the preventive aspect by enhancing the immunity, the main goal of Ayurveda can be achieved.

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